

Foreign Exchange Exposure And Firm Value Of Non-Financial Firms In Pakistan: An Empirical Study Between Derivative Users And Non-Users

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Abstract

This research investigates the impact of foreign exchange exposure on derivative users and non-users firm value of non-financial Pakistani firms for period of 2007-2018. To achieve the research objective, the descriptive-analytical method was adopted, in addition to using the data collected from the published financial and sustainability reports of the firms or those which were available on their websites, as well as the reports published of the Pakistan Stock Exchange (PSE) websites relating to the study sample. The sample consisted of 90 non-financial firms in which 55 export oriented and 35 import oriented firms listed on the Pakistan Stock Exchange, and the study was conducted over (12) years period from 2007- 2018.

Supporting the risk management use of derivative instruments, the study finds that the usage of derivative instruments significantly enhances the firm value and mitigate the foreign exchange exposure effect, with respect to operating cash flow variability in Pakistan. It is identified that the extent of risk reduction is higher in derivative user's firms as compare to non-users although the export and import oriented firms are examined combine and separately. The results show the significant positive impact regarding the relationship of derivative usage with firm's value of Pakistan non-financial firms, indicating that as Pakistan has less developed capital market and firms are less geographically diversified in comparison to other developed countries, thus the use of derivative instruments significantly enhances firm's value. GMM estimation technique is applied to test the econometric models.

INTRODUCTION

Just after Bretton Woods system of fixed exchange rates, which had been in place since 1945, fell in 1973. The majority of countries use a variable exchange rate system. Exchange rate fluctuations have been considered one of the most significant drivers of macroeconomic uncertainty (Levi, 1994; Shapiro, 1975). Due to variable exchange rate system, currency values fluctuate on a daily basis, influencing the value of a company's assets and obligations.

Therefore, foreign exchange exposure is a term used to describe how sensitive a company's value is to fluctuations in exchange rates (Shapiro, 2010). It is the degree to which a company is affected by changes in exchange rates. In addition, foreign exchange exposure, is a factor that reduces the value of exporting companies while increasing the value of importing companies due to home currency appreciation and vice versa in case of depreciating home currency. Both exporters and importers are attempting to mitigate the negative effects of foreign exchange exposure (Ihsan, Abdul & Anam, 2018).

Meanwhile, the corporation's foreign exchange exposure increased as a result of its investment in overseas markets to obtain lower-cost financing. During the Asian financial crises of 1998, a substantial number of businesses suffered significant financial losses. As a result, new preferences emerged, centered on the execution of appropriate risk management procedures. Therefore, the foregoing scenario, corporate executives began implementing risk management measures to deal with their foreign exchange exposure.

Moreover, Mason (1995) identified three fundamental ways used by corporations to cope with risk: insurance, implied diversification, and the use of derivative instruments. The insurance pays the firm's loss by using premiums that are paid on a regular basis, but it only benefits in the event of a loss. Firms, on the other hand, use diversification strategies to invest in less-than-ideal positively associated NPV projects. As a result, diversification ignores foreign exchange risk, necessitating the employment of derivatives by companies whose cash flows are prone to such risks. Following that, in the 1970s, financial derivatives were introduced as financial instruments to let corporations shift their foreign exchange exposure to other market participants.

However, according to Fabian (2010), financial regulation reform has identified derivatives as a massively complex issue. On the one hand, given the market flaws identified by Smith and Stulz (1985), using derivatives to hedge foreign exchange exposure reduces risk while increasing business value. While corporations use derivative instruments for risk taking, according to Black and Scholes (1973), when the firm's value for equity holders matches the payoff pattern of the out-of-the-money option, managers are more likely to increase the firm's risk in order to maximize the value of their option, resulting in a negative firm's value. In addition, Jensen and Meckling (1976) stated that highly a levered firm has an incentive to shift its funds from bondholders to equity holders by undertaking highly risky projects, which puts an upward and downward pressure on firm's risk and value respectively. Furthermore, adverse changes in foreign exchange rate enhance the inherent risk as a corporation which is already in a hedging position faces huge losses by the unpredictable foreign exchange exposure leading to a decrease in firm's value. Managers have also an opportunity to use derivative instruments in their own interest as they have day to day information regarding derivative trading, which increases their chances to capitalize favorable exchange rate movements, resulting in an increase in firm's risk and a decrease in firm's value. Hence the net effect of derivative usage on firm's risk and value is still an empirical question. To conclude the above argument, the value of a firm is negatively affected by the foreign exchange exposure and hedging in foreign currency derivatives saves the firm's cash flows and earnings from foreign exchange exposure. Literature depicts both manipulative and risk managing roles of derivatives as empirical evidence regarding the impact of derivative usage on firm's risk and value is still mixed. Many recent researchers analyzed hedging policy determinants and their association with some of the firm's other features, such as debt, acquisition, and growth prospects (Ahmed, Azevedo & Guney, 2014; Allayannis, 2015; Gairello, Jaime & Cristhian, 2017).

Research Problem

Due to the rapid globalization of national economies, firms are extensively affected by macroeconomic factors, and the foreign exchange exposure is one of those factors. Many businesses hesitate to grow internationally only because of the risk exposure to foreign transactions (Abdalla & Victor, 1997). Therefore, due to foreign exchange exposure firms are aiming on the significance of risk management practices and decreases the inconsistency of cash flows from international business (MacDonald, 2000). The investors/businesses can hedge the risk through various strategies including the use of foreign currency derivatives i.e. obligatory and non-obligatory derivatives (Cenedese et al., 2015; Takatoshi, 2015; Daka & Sankarshan, 2016). Academic researchers have tested the role of derivatives as a risk management instrument by examining the effect of derivative usage on firm's risk and value, although literature is mostly concentrated in countries having a developed derivative market (Nguyen and Faff, 2010; Fauver and Naranjo, 2010). Most of the researches on derivatives has been done on liquid and developed stock markets. But in emerging economies, this issue is not yet explored well. Therefore, to meet the gap the research problem for this study is formulated as: Is foreign currency derivative usage mitigate the adverse effect of foreign exchange exposure and enhance the firm value for non-financial firms listed on Pakistan Stock Exchange.

Research Objective

This research aims at testing the role of derivative usage to enhance the firm value and mitigate the adverse effect of foreign exchange exposure for non-financial firms listed in PSE.

Research Importance

The current study adds to the previous literature by addressing the risk management role of derivatives by empirically measuring whether derivative usage enhances firm value. Furthermore, in a sector-by-sector analysis, the study contributes to the existing literature by empirically analyzing whether derivative usage enhances company value while taking into account the firm's level of risk exposure. As a consequence of the study, managers should be able to establish effective risk management strategies based on the firm's natural, operational, and financial hedging instruments in order to maximize firm value while reducing risk.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Managers utilize corporate risk management approaches to reduce foreign exchange exposure. With the rapid development of financial derivative instruments, corporate risk management strategies have received a lot of attention in corporate finance theory and are playing an essential role in enterprise risk management. In their most admired study on corporate risk management, Smith and Stulz (1985) present a broad definition of hedging.

By providing an analysis, Smith and Stulz (1985) create a positive theory of hedging behavior for value-maximizing enterprises. This study was considerably distinct from the literature available at the time. Kapitsinas (2008) studied the usage and risk management practices of 62 Greece non-

financial firms for the year of 2005. Survey findings for the reason behind the firm's decision to use derivative instruments depicted that 61.9% derivative users disclosed that they used derivatives to reduce cash flow variability and 47.62% corporations used derivatives to minimize variations in accounting earnings. Corporations having foreign income or export activities were more likely to use hedging techniques in order to reduce their foreign exchange exposure, similar to the findings of Howton and Perfect (1998) and Goldberg et al. (1998). However, some studies find an insignificant relationship between foreign exchange exposure and derivative users firm value, for example, Jin and Jorian (2006), by analyzing 119 U.S. oil and gas companies, conclude that hedging fails to give any value premium, to corporations which might be due to the specific industry type. Similarly, Naito and Laux (2011), by using sample data of 434 U.S. firms, depict the insignificant effect of derivative usage, designated for hedging, on firm's value. Khediri (2010), by using sample data of 250 French non-financial firms, depicts the insignificant negative and positive impact of FCD on firm's value respectively, which is consistent with Lookman (2004) and Fauver and Naranjo (2010). By taking sample data of 468 firms/year values of Australian non-financial firms, Nguyen and Faff (2010b) identify that usage of hedging instruments and the extent of such hedging reduces firm's value. In addition, a small number of researchers have tested the relationship between foreign exchange exposure and derivative users firm value by using sample data of countries having a developing derivative market, like Gomez et al. (2009), and showed the significant positive impact of derivative usage on firm's value. Ameer (2009) found the significant positive effects of FX exposure on derivative user's firm value, measured by the market price.

Junior and Laham (2008) analyzed 212 Brazilian firms for the period of 1996-2005, and reported significant positive effect of FX exposure on derivative usage firm value. The findings were robust while considering growth rate of Tobin's Q as a dependent variable. The study suggested that value enhancing effect of derivative usage on firm value was independent of econometric method used and period analyzed.

In contrast Hamid and Bashir et al., (2013) study finds no significant impact of FX exposure on derivative user's firm value. The existing literature, comprising mostly of developed countries, shows mixed evidence regarding the determinants of derivative usage and whether such usage adds value or reduces firm's risk.

Few studies have found the speculative use of derivative instruments, as such usage of derivative instruments decreased firm value for instance; by categorizing firm's risk into primary and secondary risk, based on the revenue generated from operations, Lookman (2004) examined 364 U.S. firms per year for the period of 1999-2000 and 1992-94. By categorizing the firm's risk into primary and secondary on the basis of revenues, the study found that the hedging primary risk significantly reduced firm value, contrary to the secondary risk. The study additionally suggested that the effect of the derivative usage on firm value was mainly driven by value increasing factors that acted as a proxy of derivative usage. For an in depth analysis, the study examined that whether the relationship between firm value and production hedged was influenced by agency conflicts and managerial performance. Empirical findings showed that poor managerial performance and higher agency conflicts served as a proxy for hedging primary risk while corporations hedging secondary risk had low agency conflicts.

Whereas comparatively examined the role of derivatives as a risk management instrument in Asian countries with a developing derivative market has examined by (Alam and Talat, 2017). This study empirically examines the effect of derivative usage on firm's risk and value by employing sample data of Pakistani and Malaysian listed companies for the period of 2004-2010. Supporting the risk management use of derivative instruments, the study finds that the usage of derivative instruments significantly minimizes firm's risk, with respect to operating cash flow variability in both Pakistan and Malaysia, although the extent of risk reduction is higher in Malaysian firms. While considering variability in earning per share as a firm's risk, the findings imply that Pakistani firm's earning per share variability is irrelevant for firm's derivative usage, whereas Malaysian firms are able to minimize such volatility by using derivative instruments. The results show the insignificant effect regarding the relationship of derivative usage with firm's value of Malaysian corporations, indicating that as Malaysia has developed capital market and firms are more geographically diversified in comparison to Pakistan, thus their value relevance of derivative usage are limited. While in the case of Pakistan, the use of derivative instruments significantly enhances firm's value.

Meanwhile another study analyzes the effect of hedging for developing country the risks of foreign currency, interest rate, and commodity price on firm value as measured by Tobin's Q. The findings reveal that hedging with derivative instruments is insignificantly related to firm value but significantly varied in financial risks. Hedging for foreign currency risk has a significantly positive relation to firm value, while hedging for interest rate and commodity price risk has no relation.

Investigates the influence of control variables, such as size, profitability, age, leverage, liquidity, growth, and corporate dividends on firm value (Frensidy and Tasya, 2019).

Hadian and Cahit 2020 study examines the value effects of financial and operational hedging in a managed floating exchange rate regime with strict limitations on the trading of Malaysian Ringgit for a sample of 109 Malaysian multinationals from 2004 to 2018. Using Tobin's Q as a proxy for company value, the two-step system GMM estimation results show that, on average, derivatives hedging creates a value premium range of 7.88-8.21% in the short run, and 18.81-19.80% in the long run. The positive value effect of derivatives hedging should motivate managers of Malaysian multinationals to hedge foreign currency exposure through derivatives and encourage policymakers to take steps in developing derivatives market and products. However, the negative value effect of foreign debt hedging indicates that it destroys value. This negative effect might reflect two potential causes; higher company risk due to FC debt financing, and improper hedging practices including high costs of hedging in the underdeveloped derivatives market.

Most of the studies were done in countries having a developed derivative market, however the results are inconclusive in nature. As well as a few researchers done in developing countries but still the results are inconclusive in nature.

In the summary the present literature finds both developed and emerging economies use of derivative instruments enables corporations to mitigate the adverse effect of Exchange Rate risk through FCD.

Most studies have explored the effect of ER exposure on derivative user firm's value in countries have a developed derivative market and have positive relation between derivative usage and firm's value. The reason behind this relationship the managers are well aware of the use of derivative instruments and they hedge the risk at right time (Borokhovich et al., 2004; Clark et al., 2006; Graham and Rogers, 2002; Muller and Verschoor, 2007; Schiozer and Saito, 2009) or might firms having high leverage to use derivatives Junior (2007) and Fazillah et al. (2008). Concluding the above discussion, theoretical literature finds mixed evidence in favor of manipulation and risk management usages of derivative instruments. Therefore, the current study aim is exploring effect of ER exposure on derivative user's firm value (i-e export and import oriented separately and jointly).

H1: All derivative users' non-financial enterprises have a considerable positive association between exchange rate exposure and firm value.

H2: Users of export-oriented derivatives have a considerable positive link between exchange rate exposure and business value.

H3: Users of import-oriented derivatives have a considerable positive link between exchange rate exposure and business value.

METHODOLOGY

The aim of this research is to look at the exchange rate exposure and valuation of non-financial firms in Pakistan from 2007 to 2018. Furthermore, how exchange rate exposure influences the firm value of derivative and non-derivative users. Import-oriented and export-oriented non-financial companies listed on the Pakistan Stock Exchange are used to measure this relationship. Since financial firms are often derivative users and issuers as well as market makers, this study only considers non-financial firms. As a result, the practices of financial and non-financial companies vary drastically, potentially affecting the accuracy of outcomes. The companies that disclosed details about derivative use were chosen for the analysis. The sample included 90 non-financial businesses that met the study's goals. There are 55 export-oriented firms and 35 import-oriented firms among these firms, which are divided into two categories. Information regarding derivatives usage is available below the title of financial instruments in notes to the accounts of annual reports and the risk given at the end of the annual reports. A dummy variable 1 is assigned for hedgers and zero is assigned for non-hedgers.

Variables Calculation

Variable	Measurement	Expected Sign
Firm Value	Tobin's Q $V = \frac{(M.V \text{ of share capital} + B.V \text{ of total external debts})}{(B.V \text{ of share capital} + B.V \text{ of total external liabilities})}$ (Kim et al., 2017).	
Exchange Rate Exposure	Regression equation:	-

	$P = a + (b \times S) + e$ $b = \text{Cov}(P, S) / \text{Var}(S)$ (Allayannis et al., 2017).	
Derivative	The firms use derivatives assign 1 and non-user firms assign 0. '1' for Derivative Users '0' for Non Users (Ahmed et al., 2013; (Afza & Alam, 2017).	+ (For Users) - (Non-Users)
Liquidity	Current Ratio = current Asset / Current Liabilities (Allayannis et al., 2012).	+/-
Firm Size	Natural log of total sales (Doğan, M, 2013)	+
Leverage	Shareholder Equity / Book value of External Debt (Belghitar, 2013).	+/-

Estimated Model showing the relationship between foreign exchange exposure and derivative users firm value

H1: All derivative users' non-financial enterprises have a considerable positive association between exchange rate exposure and firm value.

$$FV = \beta_0 + \beta_1 FV_{(t-1)} + \beta_2 \text{Exposure} + \beta_3 \text{Fsize} + \beta_4 \text{CR} + \beta_5 \text{DE} + \mu \text{it}$$

H2: Users of export-oriented derivatives have a considerable positive link between exchange rate exposure and business value.

$$FVEXP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 FV_{(t-1)} + \beta_2 \text{Exposure} + \beta_3 \text{Fsize} + \beta_4 \text{CR} + \beta_5 \text{DE} + \mu \text{it}$$

H3: Users of import-oriented derivatives have a considerable positive link between exchange rate exposure and business value.

$$FVIMP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 FV_{(t-1)} + \beta_2 \text{Exposure} + \beta_3 \text{Fsize} + \beta_4 \text{CR} + \beta_5 \text{DE} + \mu \text{it}$$

Where

FV = Firm value, $FV_{(t-1)}$ = lagged dependent variable, Exposure = Exposure, CR = Current ratio, DE = Debt to Equity, Exposure = Exchange rate exposure, FVEXP = Firm value of export oriented firms, FVIMP = firm value of import oriented firms and μit = error term

Estimated Model showing the relationship between foreign exchange exposure and non-derivative users firm value

All non-derivative users have a considerable negative association between exchange rate exposure and firm value.

$$FV = \beta_0 + \beta_1 FV_{(t-1)} + \beta_2 \text{Exposure} + \beta_3 \text{Fsize} + \beta_4 \text{CR} + \beta_5 \text{DE} + \mu \text{it}$$

Exchange rate exposure and firm value of export-oriented non-derivative users have a considerable negative association.

$$FVEXP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 FV_{(t-1)} + \beta_2 \text{Exposure} + \beta_3 \text{Fsize} + \beta_4 \text{CR} + \beta_5 \text{DE} + \mu \text{it}$$

Exchange rate exposure and firm value of import-oriented non-derivative users, there is a considerable negative association.

$$FVIMP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 FV_{(t-1)} + \beta_2 \text{Exposure} + \beta_3 \text{Fsize} + \beta_4 \text{CR} + \beta_5 \text{DE} + \mu \text{it}$$

Where

FV = Firm value, $FV_{(t-1)}$ = lagged dependent variable, Exposure = Exposure, CR = Current ratio, DE = Debt to Equity, Exposure = Exchange rate exposure, FVEXP = Firm value of export oriented firms, FVIMP = firm value of import oriented firms and μit = error term

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The study analyzed firstly, the descriptive statistics to check the normality and characteristics of the data and results showed the data is normal. The second step was to conduct a correlation study. It's a mathematical technique for determining the intensity of a relationship between two numerical variables. A high correlation indicates a close relationship between two or more variables, while a weak correlation indicates that the variables are barely related. To put it another way, it's the method of analyzing the intensity of the relationship using statistical data. Therefore, if the association between variables is less than 0.5, there are no problems with multicollinearity in the variables.

However, it is premature to conclude that correlation reflects the certainty relationship between the variables without adjusting for other firm-specific and industry-specific variables. Within the estimation model, there may or may not be an exogenous relationship between the independent

variables. Finally, the current research looked at whether or not the data series used in the model is stationary. The explanation for determining whether or not the data series is stationary is that non-stationary data causes spurious regression. When a non-stationary variable is regressed using another non-stationary variable, the phenomenon of spurious regression will occur. Although the two variables may be unrelated, the results appear acceptable (having a significant coefficient and a high adjusted R²). The results of the stationary tests show that all of the variables are non-stationary at the ground, despite the fact that they initially appeared to be stationary at first difference.

After analyzing the descriptive, correlation analysis, stationary, endogeneity, and heteroscedasticity, the present study used the GMM technique to resolve the problem with endogenous regressors. When dynamic micro Panel data, essentially firm data, is used to control for endogeneity problems, GMM is an excellent tool. When researchers have endogeneity between dependent variables and want to instrument them with a lagged dependent variable, GMM is the most commonly used method. To account for the association between the explanatory variable(s) and the error term in general. (Ayturk and Serhat, 2016; Hadian et al., 2020; Haron and Anwar et al., 2021). Following Adler and Dumas (1984) and Jorion (1990), the exchange rate exposure is calculated using time series regression Jorion (1990).

The study shows the positive and significant relationship between exchange rate exposure and the valuation of all firms' derivative users. The findings are in line with Daka and Sankarshan's predictions (2019). It identifies that the exchange rate exposure creates a significant and positive impact on the firm value of derivative users. It means as the exposure increases the derivative user's firm value will also increase. This relation is highly significant at 1% level. The study also describes the positive and significant association between the dependent variable, the firm's value of all export-oriented derivative user's non-financial firms, and independent variable `exchange rate exposure Allayannis (2015). Same in the case of import-oriented user firms are positively exposed by exchange rate exposure Pramborg (2004) and Bartram et al. (2012). The control variables are Firm size (Size), Liquidity (Liq), Leverage (Lev).

Table 4.1 Estimation results between exchange rate exposure and derivative user firms

Variables	Firm value dependent variable in all columns		
	All Firms	Export Firms	Import Firms
Fv(t-1)	0.4543*** (0.0121)	0.8707*** (0.0370)	0.5896*** (0.0684)
Exposure	0.1448*** (0.0578)	0.05068*** (0.0186)	0.5228*** (0.2049)
Size	-0.0764** (0.03586)	0.0358*** (0.0110)	0.3545*** (0.1473)
Liq	-0.0088** (0.0044)	-0.0051** (0.0024)	-0.0859 (0.0606)
Lev	0.0826*** (0.0062)	0.0003 (0.0050)	0.1161** (0.0542)
Cons	0.6972** (0.3461)	-0.3322*** (0.1155)	4.48262*** (1.61933)
AR(1)	0.017	0.033	0.021
AR(2)	0.393	0.261	0.057
Sargan/Hansen	0.135	0.272	0.335
No of groups	57	37	20
No of Instruments	27	23	17

Note: The results of the two-step system generalized method of moment (GMM) dynamic panel model are presented in Table 4.1. The firm value, as determined by Tobin's Q, is the dependent variable (TQ). Columns II, III, and IV contain the results of FV(t-1), Exposure, Size, Liq, and Lev, respectively. The proxies variables are Exposure, Firm size (Size), Liquidity(Liq), Leverage (Ler). The presence of first-order serial correlation is demonstrated by the significant value of AR(1), indicating that the null hypothesis of no first difference autocorrelation among the error terms is rejected. AR(2), on the other hand, is negligible, indicating that there is no second order serial

correlation in level regression among error terms. The overbid value of the Sargan/Hansen test is negligible, meaning that the instruments are accurate and not over-identified. GMM is correctly defined with no recognition problems, according to the overall results of AR (1), AR (2), and the Sargan/Hansen test.

In the second phase of analysis, the association between exposure and non-derivative user firms' value has a significant and inverse relation Erdogan (2016). It means as the exposure increase the non-derivative user's firm's value will decrease (Zhang and Ouyang, 2020; Simakova, 2017). This relation is highly significant at a 5% level. The estimation results identified notable inverse relation of exchange rate exposure with a value of non-derivative user firms engaged in exports (Zarei et al., 2020); Shekhar, 2016). The findings indicated that a high exposure in the exchange rate would more likely decrease the value of firms that are engaged in international operations. According to the results, a highly significant and negative relationship exists between exchange rate exposure and firms value of non-derivative import users at a 1% level of significance.

Table 4.2 Estimation results between exchange rate exposure and non-derivative users

Variables	All firms	Export firms	Import firms
Fv(t-1)	0.9661*** (0.0232)	0.6142*** (0.1008)	0.7897** (0.0615)
Exposure	-0.1269*** (0.0568)	-0.1190*** (0.0384)	-0.7458 (0.2305)
Size	-0.0348*** (0.0213)	0.0735*** (0.0220)	0.3690 (0.0672)
Liq	0.04327*** (0.0103)	0.1329*** (0.0251)	-0.4527 (0.1817)
Lev	0.0026*** (0.0094)	0.0029 (0.0025)	0.3443 (0.0803)
Cons	0.2638*** (0.2045)	-0.7857 (0.2197)	-3.4368 (0.7457)
AR(1)	0.036	0.018	0.054
AR(2)	0.978	0.497	0.542
Sargan/Hansen	0.545	0.256	0.466
No of groups	34	19	15
No of Instruments	25	17	11

Note: Table 4.3 reports the results related to the two-step system generalized method of moment (GMM) dynamic panel model. The dependent variable is the firm's value measured through Tobin's Q (TQ). The results of $FV_{(t-1)}$, Exposure, Size, Liq, Lev presents in Columns II, III, IV respectively. The proxy's variables are Exposure, firm size (Size), Liquidity (Liq), Leverage (Lev). The presence of first-order serial correlation is demonstrated by the significant value of AR (1), indicating that the null hypothesis of no first difference autocorrelation among the error terms is rejected. AR (2), on the other hand, is negligible, indicating that there is no second order serial correlation in level regression among error terms. The overbid value of the Sargan/Hansen test is negligible, meaning that the instruments are accurate and not over-identified. GMM is correctly defined with no recognition problems, according to the overall results of AR (1), AR (2), and the Sargan/Hansen test.

CONCLUSION

The aim of the research is to determine the relationship between exchange rate exposure and the valuation of firms that use derivatives and non-derivatives. The target demographic consisted of businesses that engage in foreign trade, such as imports and exports. The analysis focused on non-financial companies that were listed on the Pakistan stock exchange between 2007 and 2018. The models are estimated using the GMM technique. The researcher estimated the relationship between derivative user's firm value and exchange rate exposure, and using the GMM process, it was discovered that there is a strong and positive relationship between derivative use and exchange rate exposure for both import and export focused firms individually and collectively. According to the findings, there is often a significant and positive relationship between exchange rate exposure and derivative use. Based on the findings, it can be concluded that while exchange rate exposure can affect a firm's cash flow, derivative use reduces cash flow volatility and increases the firm's value.

Recommendation

Based on the findings, businesses should monitor and manage their exchange rate risk exposure because it can impact the valuation of their companies. Businesses must handle them in the most effective way possible in order to increase their corporate value. Since in export oriented firms, exposure relates positively with corporate value in short run only (in case of home currency depreciate against foreign currency) however in long run both export and import both firms negatively exposed by exchange rate exposure. The businesses must consider the following things while managing the exposure and deciding about the usage of derivatives:

- As, the fluctuation in exchange rate, in any direction will differently affect the import oriented and export oriented firms. That's why the businesses have to cope up the same situation according to their state of affairs. If the currency value is expected to depreciate in response to the foreign currency, then it is positive for the export oriented firms while same thing will adversely affect the import oriented firms.
- The businesses must use technical or market based analysis to predict the exchange rate fluctuations in the upcoming periods.
- If the predicted exchange rate is favorable for the firm, then there is no need to use the derivative instrument as in this situation derivative usage will pose only extra cost to the firm. Otherwise firm need to use hedging instruments if the cost of using derivative is less than the cost of loss due to exchange rate.

Limitations of the study

Since this research is based on data from the manufacturing industry, the findings cannot be applied to firms in the banking and service industries. Due to the lack of data in some sectors, the sample size is limited.

Future Prospects

The analysis can be expanded in the future by classifying derivatives as foreign exchange derivatives, interest rate derivative and Islamic derivatives and compare which type of derivative highly effects firms value.

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